

Harmonised dilation test procedure

SPONSORED BY THE

Federal Ministry
of Education
and Research

UNIVERSITÄT
BAYREUTH

Bayerisches Zentrum für Batterietechnik

Kompetenzcluster
Analytik & Qualitätssicherung

Electrical
Energy Systems

Table of contents

i.	Acknowledgement	3
ii.	Executive Summary	3
1.	Introduction.....	5
2.	Reference conditions and definitions	6
2.1	Reference conditions	6
2.2	Definitions	6
2.3	Measurement equipment.....	7
3.	Test stand	8
3.1	Dilation measurement methods.....	8
3.2	Mechanical design specifications and recommendations	11
3.3	Exemplary test stand design.....	13
4.	Setting boundary conditions for repeatable measurements.....	16
4.1	Viscoelasticity of cells.....	16
4.2	Thermal expansion behaviour	16
4.3	Capacity measurement procedure	17
4.4	Post-formation.....	19
5.	Test procedure for dilation analysis	20
5.1	OCT and maximal expansion at Begin of Life	20
5.2	Hysteresis	21
5.3	Power dependency	22
5.4	Irreversible expansion rate under standard cycling conditions.....	23
5.5	Maximal expansion at End of Life	24
	References.....	Fehler! Textmarke nicht definiert.

List of figures

Figure 1: Sketch of a representative test stand using a dial gauge for dilation measurement...	8
Figure 2: Sketch of a representative test stand using a pressure plate and contact displacement sensor for dilation measurement.....	9
Figure 3: Sketch of a contact-free dilation measurement test stand.	9
Figure 4: Sketch of a strain gauge sensor.	10
Figure 5: Cell holder of the proposed test stand design for dilation measurement on pouch cells.	13
Figure 6: exemplary relaxation behaviour of pouch cells after applying 0.2 MPa pressure. ...	16
Figure 7: thermal expansion behaviour of a lithium-ion battery.....	17
Figure 8: Change of the coulombic efficiency over the first ten cycles after formation.	19
Figure 9: Differences between pOCT and iOCT in a) and influence of the pressure on the OCT in b).	20
Figure 10: expansion and second derivative of expansion during charge e.g. for the identification of graphite stages.....	21
Figure 11: Hysteresis loops displaying the change in dilation depending on prior min. and max. SOCs with a close up.....	22
Figure 12: Results of discharging with varying C-rates with the dilation shown in a) and the voltage shown in b).	23
Figure 13: Irreversible change in thickness over cycle life in a) and reversible expansion over cycles in b).	24
Figure 14: expansion during pOCV measurement at EOL in a) and BOL in b).....	25

i. Acknowledgement

The test protocol was developed as a part of the project “analysis of the hysteresis and aging via calorimetry and dilatometry” (HysKaDi). The project was funded by the German federal ministry for education and research (BMBF) under funding reference 03XP0321A.

The authors thank the BMBF for the funding, Alexander Kunz, and Andreas Jossen (TUM EES), Clara Berg, and Hubert Gasteiger (TUM TEC) and Sanaz Banifarsi, Abdelaziz A. Abdel-Latif and Margret Wohlfahrt-Mehrens (ZSW) for the fruitful discussion and productive cooperation.

ii. Executive Summary

For optimal use of Lithium-Ion batteries (LIB), especially at challenging tasks like fast charging at low temperatures, the knowledge of the internal state of the cell is crucial. Conclusions on the internal states can among others be drawn by monitoring the flow of charge to and from the cell and by taking the characteristic voltage curve into account. Like the voltage, the thickness of the cell is changing with the state of charge (SOC) of the cell. The change in thickness is hereby nearly exclusively caused by the anode since the expansion of most cathode materials are neglectable. The understanding of the dilation behaviour of cells can therefore give additional information about the state of the anode. The dilation benefits from the fact that it is not altered by polarisation effects like charge transfer and the behaviour does not change for different cathode materials. Unfortunately, keeping precise track of the dilation is only possible for pouch cells and, at the current state of research, highly precise dilation sensors are needed.

Nevertheless, in recent years a growing number of publications are dealing with the dilation behaviour and application of dilation analysis in LIBs. Especially in combination with pressure variation and the perspective on next-generation materials with significantly larger volume expansion like silicon this research is promising. Due to the novelty of the raising attention neither the methods nor the procedures are established. In consequence, the hurdle for the application of dilation measurements is quite high, since the test stand must be developed, designed, and build and the experimenter needs experience to accomplish repeatable measurements. Additionally, even if the step towards dilation studies is taken the low level of standardization leads to a variety of different measurements setups and measurement results of varying quality and low level of comparability.

By describing approved test stands, measurement methods and procedures in the following chapters we aim to lower the hurdle of starting dilation measurements on the one side and improve the quality and comparability of these results on the other side. We begin with giving basic reference conditions and definitions to assure that the procedures are well understood for every level of experience. After that an overview over different dilation measurement techniques is given with the matching literature for further studies. In addition, an example of a test stand for dilation measurements is given. To prepare for repeatable measurements the necessary preparations are listed and examples for the results are given. From here on different test procedures are explained which give valuable insights on the dilation behaviour of LIBs.

1. Introduction

Energy storage systems are the key enablers for the decarbonization of the transport and energy sector. While hydrogen fuel cells and power-to-X are promising candidates for seasonal storages and sector coupling, the market for batteries in grid-scale storage applications is rapidly growing [1]. Additionally, batteries are currently the most promising option as energy storage for zero-emission vehicles. While there are different battery chemistries available, the Lithium-ion battery (LIB) has since its introduction in 1992 by Sony [2] become the dominant storage technology for portable electronics, home storage and battery electric vehicles.

Further development since then has constantly increased the LIB in terms of safety, cost, energy density and power density. Nevertheless, the complex electrochemical system is not yet fully understood. Especially the expansion behaviour of LIBs has just recently seen growing attention in research efforts. While some are solely describing the dilation behaviour, a raising number of publications aims to use the dilation analysis for insights into the electrochemical states of the LIB.

To further discuss the benefits and limits of applying dilation measurements on LIBs the structure of these is briefly explained. LIBs consist of a negative electrode which is independently of the direction of the electrochemical reaction referred to as anode and a positive electrode similar independently called cathode. Both electrodes are segregated by a separator and ionically connected by the electrolyte. The whole assembly is protected by a hull which usually comes in one of three forms: solid cylindrical, solid prismatic or in a soft prismatic bag, called pouch. While the cathode changes with the field of application of the cell, often determining the name given to the battery (e.g. LFP, NMC or NCA) the anode for commercial applications today is merely exclusively made from graphite. While the integration of silicon or lithium-metal as anode in LIB has long been scope of various research efforts, pure next-generation anode materials do not yet make a significant share of commercial cells. Nevertheless, recently a growing number of manufacturers are building cells with mixed Si/C or SiO_x/C anodes.

Since the used anode materials show a significant change in volume during lithiation, with graphite expanding roughly 10 % upon full-lithiation being on the lower end of the scale [3–5], while cathode materials show close to no change in volume during use, in the following explanation of the different storage mechanisms will be focused on the anode materials. As the most common anode material graphite is an intercalation electrode, where the lithium-ions enter the graphite structure at the defect sites and locate themselves in the centre of the hexagonal carbon rings [6]. At entering of the lithium-ions the distance of the graphene layers that make up graphite is increased. Since the layers are filled successively, forming distinct phases and phase transitions that are distinguishable in the open circuit voltage (OCV) of the electrode, the course of lithiation is visible in the expansion as well. The second material that is analysed with dilation measurements is silicon. In contrast to graphite, silicon is an alloying electrode that forms different alloys with lithium, leading to a significant expansion. Due to the lack of multiple phase transformation during lithiation, the expansion behaviour of silicon is almost proportional to the degree of lithiation [7].

2. Reference conditions and definitions

For comparable measurements certain reference conditions are defined. This reference conditions contain:

- Temperature
- Pressure on the cell

To assure comparable results the cells should be stored at reference pressure for at least 48 h and at reference temperature for at least 12 h. All tests must be performed inside a climate chamber to assure for constant temperature.

2.1 Reference conditions

The dilation behaviour changes significantly with temperature of the cell and pressure applied onto the cells surface. Therefore, reference conditions are defined to improve the comparability of different measurement results. The reference conditions for the dilation protocol are:

Variable	Symbol	Standard unit	Reference condition
Charge current	I_{ch}	A	(0.5*Nominal Capacity) A
Discharge current	I_{dch}	A	(-0.5*Nominal Capacity) A
Temperature	T	°C	25 °C
Pressure	P	MPa	0.2 MPa

2.2 Definitions

In the following basic definitions for procedures and battery states are made.

State of Charge (SOC):

The State of Charge is defined as the relation between the amount of charge currently stored inside the battery and the amount of charge that can be stored with the defined capacity measurement procedure without violating the voltage limits.

Dilation and expansion:

The dilation of the cell is the change in cell thickness under different conditions. The dilation depends on various parameters like temperature, pressure, and SOC of the cell. In contrary to the cell's voltage, the dilation does not only change with the used electrode chemistry, but with the areal capacity of the cell. While the absolute value of expansion is an important value to account for e.g. the mechanical stability of an battery assembly, for the comparison of different cells the dilation should always be referenced to a suitable cell thickness value. This normalized form of the dilation will be called expansion. The dilation measurement under equilibrium conditions over the SOC is in wake of the OCV called open-circuit thickness (OCT).

Formation:

The process of building boundary layers on the electrode particles in a lithium-ion battery is called formation. This process is mainly happening during the first charge of the battery,

meaning the first lithiation of the anode. While in the literature three full cycles are considered sufficient formation, a widely accepted definition when formation ends, and the cycle life of a battery starts does not exist. Therefore, in this document the end of formation is defined as the point in the battery's cycle life where the coulombic efficiency

$$\eta_c = \frac{Q_{dch}}{Q_{ch}}$$

reaches a value that is expected for the DUT's chemistry (e.g. 99.9 % for state-of-the-art lithium-ion batteries).

Begin of Life (BOL):

The Begin of Life of the battery is where the formation process is completed, and a stable coulomb efficiency is reached.

End of Life (EOL):

The End of Life is reached as soon as the battery shows less than 70% of the capacity measured at BOL with the defined capacity measurement procedure.

State of Health (*SOH*):

The State of Health is the capacity measured with the defined measurement procedure in relation to the capacity at BOL.

$$SOH = \frac{Q_{dch,BOL}}{Q_{dch}}$$

Current rate (C-rate)

The current rate is used to set the cell load into relation to the cell's capacity. The unit of the current rate is $1/h$ but usually the capital letter C is used. E.g., 1C is the constant current that equals the cells nominal capacity when flowing for an hour:

$$1 \cdot \frac{Q_{nom}}{1 \text{ h}} = 1C$$

2.3 Measurement equipment

With the use of designated battery test equipment, the most important requirements for current and voltage measurement precision are usually met. For the dilation test procedure described in section 5 the test stand should be able to provide a current up to 1C. To correctly assign the dilation measurement to the current and voltage signal, the used tester should have additional interfaces to integrate analogue or digital signals.

The used dilation sensor should be able to provide a resolution of at least $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ % of the cells thickness to be able to properly measure features of batteries with graphitic anodes.

3. Test stand

In chapter three the important parameter and design specifications are discussed and several methods for dilation measurements from literature are shown. Additionally, an exemplary test stand design for efficient testing of commercial small format pouch cells is shown.

3.1 Dilation measurement methods

For the precise determination of the change in expansion of the cell several methods are applicable. In the following several methods with advantages and disadvantages are discussed. Furthermore, literature with matching test stands and exemplary measurement results are given.

Contact-based dilation measurements

The most common method in literature is using a contact displacement sensor or dial gauge positioned above the LIB to measure the change in expansion. Early publications usually used a dial gauge with the sensor tip placed directly on the cell without applying homogeneous pressure to the pouch bag [8–12]. A representative version of such setup is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Sketch of a representative test stand using a dial gauge for dilation measurement.

While the simplicity of the design is appealing, the test stand design has some drawbacks. The first issue is that the dial gauge only measures the change in a single spot. This may lead to significant measurement errors since the expansion of the cell is often not homogeneous, especially at high rates (which was shown by dilation tests with laser distance sensors [13]). The single contact point implies another problem. If no additional force, by adding a spring to the sensor tip or similar, is brought on the cell, the dilation measurement is easily distorted by gas evolution. If a spring is added to prevent this, the local pressure difference may affect the cell's behaviour by favouring higher local current densities [14]. Finally, the uncompressed LIB pouch is neither a realistic application scenario and will lead to overestimation of cell degradation by delamination and similar ageing mechanisms caused by the volume expansion [15].

To tackle the above-mentioned issues, another test stand design using a contact displacement sensor came up in various publications [15–18]. The decisive difference between both designs is an additional plate above the LIB, that is pressed down by springs. The cell is therefore under homogeneous pressure, which displays more realistic application conditions and prevents degradation mechanisms like delamination. Additionally, the plate prevents local impact of the

contact-based measurement and equals out inhomogeneous expansion in the measurement. A sketch of the test stand principle is given in Figure 2.

For even an even closer estimation of realistic boundary conditions of the pressure applied on LIBs during their application, the above design principal is extended by pneumatic cylinders. These are used to actively control the pressure applied to the cell [19–21]. The method of dilation measurement though remains similar.

Figure 2: Sketch of a representative test stand using a pressure plate and contact displacement sensor for dilation measurement.

Contact-free dilation measurement

For a contact-free measurement of cell dilation several test stand designs using laser distance sensor were published [13,22,23]. These setups offer two distinct advantages. The first advantage is the fact, that the measurement is not interfering in any way with the cell. Local pressure differences due to the measurement method are therefore excluded and the cells behaviour is not altered. The second advantage is the measuring over the whole cell surface is possible. To achieve this the sensor head is usually linearly moved along the cell's length axis, as illustrated in Figure 3. This enables the analysis of the homogeneity of the cell's volume change and therefore may give information of locally resolved states of lithiation.

Figure 3: Sketch of a contact-free dilation measurement test stand.

The disadvantage of the described method is that applying pressure on the cell is not easily possible. Therefore, in most cases the operating conditions of the cells is not realistically

depicted. Especially the cells aging behaviour may be overexaggerated, caused by the reasons already mentioned before.

Strain gauge sensors

While all the above methods can display the cells dilation behaviour with high resolution during cycling of the cell, the setups are limited to a laboratory use. Due to high cost and large installation space of the setups the use in a real-world application is not realistically possible. To enable dilation measurements in technical applications and stretch the field of application on cell formats with a hard case, some publications are suggesting the use of strain gauge sensors [24,25]. While enabling dilation measurements at low cost and minimal installation space, the resulting signal has a low resolution and is strongly altered by noise. Additionally, the orientation of the sensor makes a significant difference, consequently, the application of the sensors on the cell must be done with care.

Figure 4: Sketch of a strain gauge sensor.

Literature overview

Table 1: Literature overview for different methods and applications for dilation measurements.

Application	Measurement method	References
Open-Circuit dilation behaviour	Contact-based dilation measurement	[8,11,17,21,26]
	Strain gauge sensor	[24]
Dynamic dilation behaviour	Contact-based dilation measurement	[9]
Plating analysis and fast charging	Contact-based dilation measurement	[10,12,16]
	Contact-free dilation measurement	[13,22]
Pressure and ageing	Contact-based dilation measurement	[15,18,20]
Proof of concept	Contact-based dilation measurement	[19]
	Strain gauge sensor	[25]

3.2 Mechanical design specifications and recommendations

The test stand must suffice basic specifications for the reliable and reproducible measurement of the dilation behaviour of LIBs. Furthermore, some specifications will be added, that are not essential but will improve results and handling of the test stand. The following list gives an overview about the specifications that are closer discussed in this section.

Necessary specifications:

- constant pressure on the cell
- homogeneous pressure on the cell
- distance measurement with high resolution
- high stiffness of the test stand

Optional specifications:

- good thermal coupling of the cell and test stand
- low temperature expansion
- separate device for cell clamping

For the repeatable measurement of the dilation behaviour of LIBs being able to apply constant pressure on the cell is a key requirement. Due to the elasticity of the cell components, the expansion of the cell depends on the external pressure. If the pressure changes with the expansion of the cell, the measurement expansion itself will change. Consequently, to make dilation measurements comparable, the pressure must be well defined even under varying internal states and environmental conditions.

Furthermore, it is necessary to assure for a homogeneous pressure. As shown in several publications listed in section 3.1 the cell behaviour and aging is changing with the pressure. Areas under higher pressure for example will tend to experience locally increased current densities leading to locally confined degradation mechanisms. Inhomogeneous pressure may therefore alter the result of aging experiments significantly. Additionally, metallic lithium deposition influences the expansion behaviour of the cell, which may distort the dilation signal.

The necessary resolution of the used dilation sensor is highly depended on the device under test. Cells with many stacked or wound electrode layers or with materials like silicon on the anode will experience more expansion. Consequently, a lower resolution of the sensor will give sufficient information. To track relaxation processes and degradation mechanisms a sensor resolution less than $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ % of the maximum expansion is suggested. A rough estimation is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Estimation of the necessary sensor resolution for different cells

Cell type	Capacity	Sensor resolution
Single layer cell/ single electrode	~	50 nm
Small format pouch cell	< 5 Ah	< 1 μ m
Large format pouch cell	> 5 Ah	< 2 μ m

For cells with a large surface area, the forces to reach technically significant pressure levels will exceed several thousand Newton. Therefore, the test stand and especially the pressure plates should be designed in a way, that the deformation remains below the resolution of the sensor used.

The expansion of the cell does not only depend on the inner state of the LIB and the pressure applied upon it, but additionally on the temperature. While later in this document a test to determine the temperature expansion coefficient of the cell is described for the correction of the dilation data, ideally the cell influence of the cell's temperature is minimized from the start. Therefore, it is beneficial to construct the test stand in a way so that the thermal coupling between cell and test stand is good. This will help to keep the cell temperature close to ambient level and reduce distortions of the dilation measurement. To prevent the cell from heating up the test stand and by this cause errors in the dilation measurement, the test stand should be sufficiently able to transfer heat to the ambient.

The test stand itself is changing with the temperature. This may change the pressure applied to the cell and distort the dilation signal. The test stand should be designed in a manner that the used material has a low thermal expansion coefficient or that the changes in length only slightly affect the measurement.

Design recommendations

Due to high precision, possible use under constant pressure and easy and cheap implementation the contact displacement sensor setup is recommended. This method will therefore be solely discussed in the following description of the test stand. The tests described later in the document though may be performed with any test stand.

For the construction of a custom test stand for the dilation measurement using a single contact displacement sensor on a cell under constant pressure some recommendations are stated for high repeatability and improved handling.

For the constant and homogeneous application of pressure on the cell it is recommended to compress the cell between to plates. The upper plate should be vertically movable. To assure parallelism between the lower and upper plate, the upper plate should be attached to the test stand by slide bearings with guideway. To apply force for the compression springs with varying spring constant are the simplest solution. It should be made sure that the springs are interchangeable, so that the correct spring constant for the aimed pressure is used to minimize the change in pressure by the expansion of the cell. This additionally improves the flexibility of the test stand, e.g., for the later use of a fixed compression or actively controlled components.

For an easier handling of the test stand, less needed space inside of climate chambers during testing, and lower cost of the whole setup, it is recommended to separate the test stand and the setup for applying force to the cell. A compression bank with integrated force sensor and pneumatic force application assures quick setup of the desired pressure on the cell and good repeatability of several cells are supposed to be compressed. If an ideally constant pressure on the cell is wanted, the use of pneumatic components like pneumatic cylinders or balloons are

recommended, with the downside of making the setup more complicated and the necessary availability of compressed air at the testing side.

3.3 Exemplary test stand design

In the following the design and cost of an exemplary test stand is shown. The specifications of the test stand are:

- maximum cell size of 160/85/15 mm (L/W/H)
- maximum pressure for the largest possible cell format of 1 MPa
- maximum ampacity of 60 A
- 4-wire measurement

The proposed test stand design consists of a cell holder and a separate clamping unit. While the cell holder is needed for each test channel, a single version of the clamping unit is sufficient for multiple cell holder. The dilation of the clamped pouch cell is measured by a contact displacement sensor in contact with an aluminium plate upon the cell under test.

The cell holder is shown in Figure 5 and used to keep a constant and homogeneous pressure on the cell by two parallel aluminium plates. The parallelism is assured by installing the upper plate with plain bearings along four guide columns. The pressure is held up by fixing the top plate along the spring guidance. The springs can be exchanged and therefore spring constants chosen that match the needed force for compression. The clamping unit is equipped with a pneumatic cylinder and a load cell to precisely and repeatably apply force by air pressure. After clamping the cell holder can be removed from the clamping unit and tested in a different environment.

Figure 5: Cell holder of the proposed test stand design for dilation measurement on pouch cells.

Technical drawings with an overview of parts and prices are given below. For further information and CAD files contact ees@uni-bayreuth.de.

Pouch cell holder

Parts	Amount	Cost
Guide column	4 Pcs.	220 €
Plain bearing bush	4 Pcs.	130 €
Clamp (plain bearing)	24 Pcs.	45 €
Profile rail	0.25 m	5 €
Push-rod tensioner	2 Pcs.	30 €
Contact pin	2 Pcs.	-
Contact glider	2 Pcs.	-
Bottom plate	1 Pc.	-
Cell support	1 Pc.	-
Pressure plate	1 Pc.	-
Clamp plate	1 Pc.	-
Spring	4 Pcs.	20 €
Spring guidance	4 Pcs.	-
Clamp (spring guide)	2 Pcs.	-
Total cost (without own contributions)		450 €

4. Setting boundary conditions for repeatable measurements

In the following chapter the test procedure for a repeatable dilation analysis of lithium-ion pouch cells is described together with hints for the standardized evaluation scripts.

4.1 Viscoelasticity of cells

Lithium-ion batteries usually show a viscoelastic deformation behaviour. Measuring this behaviour for the use of correction is difficult since clamping of the cell and start of the dilation measurement are usually timely separated and additionally overlaid by thermal effects. Therefore, it is suggested to make sure that the deformation processes due to external pressure can be neglected by letting the cell rest under pressure for at least 48h. For extra security it is recommended to track the change in cell thickness and make sure that the change in contraction is less than $2.5 \cdot 10^{-2} \% \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ before the begin of measurement.

The relaxation of a pouch cell after being clamped with 0.2 MPa pressure is exemplarily shown in Figure 6. The relaxation behaviour is given as dilation and as expansion referenced to the nominal cell thickness.

Figure 6: exemplary relaxation behaviour of pouch cells after applying 0.2 MPa pressure.

4.2 Thermal expansion behaviour

The volume of most material is dependent on its temperature. The thermal expansion coefficient should therefore be initially determined to estimate the influence of temperature changes inside the battery on the measured dilation signal. At first the examined temperature range should be determined. This depends on the used dilation sensor, the temperature limits of the cell and the available temperatures of the climate chamber. For the described procedure a temperature range from 0 °C to 40 °C is chosen.

The test must be performed once with and without a clamped in cell to account for the expansion of the test stand. The test stand is pressurised with the reference pressure and placed inside a climate chamber. Then the while constantly tracking the dilation signal the following procedure is conducted:

Test procedure:

1. Let the test stand rest in the climate chamber for 24 h at the lowest temperature.

- a. In case that a cell is clamped inside the test stand consider pressure relaxation behaviour described in 4.1.
2. Increase the temperature by 5 °C and let the test stand rest for at least 4 h.
3. Repeat step 2 until the upper temperature limit is reached.

Evaluation:

- The expansion of the test stand during temperature change is visible as a contraction of the cell in the dilation signal. Therefore, this signal should be subtracted from the dilation measurement with a clamped in cell.
- Plot the resulting difference in cell thickness in reference to the lower temperature limit over the temperature.
- Fit a linear curve to the datapoints. The resulting slope of the curve is the thermal expansion coefficient of the cell.

An exemplary test result is shown in Figure 7. Publications using a similar procedure are by Bauer et al. [9] or Jahn et al. [16].

Figure 7: thermal expansion behaviour of a lithium-ion battery.

4.3 Capacity measurement procedure

The procedure is on the one hand used to determine the remaining useful capacity of the cell. On the other hand, this displays the standard load profile used for cycling. This use of a standardized procedure enables the restoration of similar electrochemical states inside the LIB.

Test procedure:

1. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
2. Charge with constant current stated in the data sheet until the upper cut-off voltage is reached. If no value is given charge with the defined reference current rate.
3. Charge with constant voltage until the cut-off current stated in the data sheet is reached. If no value is stated use 0.1C.
4. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
5. Discharge with constant current stated in the data sheet until the upper cut-off voltage is reached. If no value is given charge with the defined reference current rate.

6. Discharge with constant voltage until the cut-off current stated in the data sheet is reached. If no value is stated use 0.1C.

Evaluation:

- Calculate the charge throughput during constant current and constant voltage discharge phase.

4.4 Post-formation

Since the growth of the SEI is indeed measurable with the precise contact displacement sensors, making sure that the formation of boundary layers is mostly finished is crucial. The number of cycles that are additionally necessary until a constant Coulombic efficiency is reached, varies from cell to cell. As procedure for a first estimation, in case that the cell is unknown to the experimenter, the following procedure is suggested.

Test procedure:

1. Perform five full cycles with the capacity estimation procedure and calculate the coulombic efficiency.
2. Add additional full cycles until the coulombic efficiency reaches a stable plateau.

Evaluation:

- Determine the charge throughput during charge Q_{ch} and during the following discharge Q_{dch} and calculate the coulombic efficiency with the following equation:

$$\eta_{\text{C}} = \frac{Q_{\text{dch}}}{Q_{\text{ch}}}$$

An exemplary course of the coulombic efficiency for 10 cycles of post-formation is given in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Change of the coulombic efficiency over the first ten cycles after formation.

5. Test procedure for dilation analysis

In this chapter the test procedures for the description of the dilation behaviour of LIBs are given and some exemplary results are shown. The test procedure starts with the measurement of the quasi-static dilation behaviour of the cell. For more advanced analysis of the dilation behaviour, two further test procedures will show the measurement of the dilation hysteresis and the deviation of the dilation curve from the OCT depending on the current rate. Afterwards the irreversible expansion during aging is tested. Finally, the expansion behaviour at BOL and EOL is compared.

5.1 OCT and maximal expansion at Begin of Life

The dilation behaviour of the cell at BOL depends on the material used in the cell. As the expansion of cathode materials is often negligible, the thickness profile over the SOC can be used to analyse the anode material. In contrary to the cell voltage, the dilation behaviour does not show highly dynamic changes. Therefore, the differences between OCT curves taken by low constant current measurements (marked with pOCT in Figure 9 a)) do not differ extensively from curves taken with galvanostatic intermittent titration techniques (marked with iOCT in Figure 9 a)). While the pressure has significant impact on the ageing of the cell as well as the settling behaviour after compression, the influence on the OCT is only small (see Figure 9 b)).

Figure 9: Differences between pOCT and iOCT in a) and influence of the pressure on the OCT in b).

The following test procedure is proposed to determine the OCT and the maximum cell expansion at BOL:

Test procedure:

1. Let the cell rest for at least 48 h.
2. Discharge with CC-CV until lower cut-off voltage and cut-off current of $1/20C$.
3. Let the cell rest for 10 min.
4. Charge with constant current of $1/20C$ until reaching upper cut-off voltage.
5. Let the cell rest for 10 min.
6. Discharge with constant current of $1/20C$ until reaching lower cut-off voltage.

Optional:

- To avoid accelerating aging during storage charge with 1C to 50 % of the nominal capacity.

Evaluation:

- Plot the measured expansion over the charge throughput or normalized charge throughput.
- Calculate the second derivative of the expansion with respect to the charge throughput and plot the result over the charge throughput or normalized charge throughput (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: expansion and second derivative of expansion during charge e.g. for the identification of graphite stages.

5.2 Hysteresis

The hysteresis behaviour of cells is quite different from the voltage and therefore the knowledge about it may help to get a better understanding of the inner states of the cell. The hysteresis behaviour is approximated with low constant current measurement. While there are different equal approaches to estimate the hysteresis behaviour for the cell voltage, the hysteresis of the dilation is strongly dependent on the last reached extrema of the SOC. Therefore, it is suggested to measure the dilation hysteresis by starting at 50 % SOC and run a series of growing hysteresis loops. Running hysteresis tests with growing hysteresis window always starting or ending at the same SOC is not suitable to display the full range of possible resulting dilation states. The resulting measurement of seven loops starting with the smallest loop (30 % - 70 %) going up in 5 % steps to a full cycle is plotted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Hysteresis loops displaying the change in dilation depending on prior min. and max. SOC with a close up.

Test procedure:

1. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
2. Charge to 50 % of the prior measured real capacity with a constant current of $1/2C$.
3. Let the cell rest for 1 hour.
4. Charge $n \cdot 5$ % of the measured capacity with a constant current of $1/20C$, with n being the number of the current loop.
5. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
6. Discharge $n \cdot 10$ % of the measured capacity with a constant current of $1/20C$.
7. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
8. Charge $n \cdot 5$ % of the measured capacity with a constant current of $1/20C$.
9. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
10. Repeat the steps 4 – 9 for 11 times. The first hysteresis loop should be repeated once.

Evaluation:

- Split the single loops and plot voltage and dilation for each over the SOC.

5.3 Power dependency

One of the biggest advantages of the dilation measurement is that the expansion of the cell is not altered by voltage drops over the internal resistance of the cell. Due to diffusion limitations inside the particles and lithiation gradient over the electrode's thickness, the dilation still changes depending on the current rate with which the cell is subjected. As shown in Figure 12 a) the dilation is linearized with higher currents but is much closer to the open circuit thickness compared to the voltage (Figure 12 b)).

Figure 12: Results of discharging with varying C-rates with the dilation shown in a) and the voltage shown in b).

Test procedure:

1. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
2. Charge with CC-CV until the upper cut-off voltage is reached and the current has fallen below $1/20C$.
3. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
4. Discharge with a constant current of $n \cdot 1/2C$, with n being the number of the current loop.
5. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
6. Repeat the steps 2 – 5 for 6 times.

Evaluation:

- Calculate the discharged capacity and change in thickness for every discharge.
- Plot the resulting capacity and thickness change of the discharge rate.
- Plot the course of the voltage and dilation signal over the SOC for the discharge phase.

5.4 Irreversible expansion rate under standard cycling conditions

To account for changes in thickness over the cycle life the resulting irreversible increase in thickness as well as the course of the maximum expansion must be evaluated. In this context it is important to recognise that the dilation behaviour over the cycle life is changing with the underlying degradation mechanism accountable for the loss of available capacity. The deposition of metallic lithium (LD) on the anode leads to a significant increase in cell expansion. This is true for reversible forms of LD that will later lead to a decrease of the expansion as well as irreversible LD. Therefore, the following test cannot display all different possible trajectories of degradation mechanisms and their effects on the dilation behaviour. To make an educated guess on the expected expansion behaviour under standard cycling conditions, the following test is suggested. Repeating it for extreme cycling conditions is optional to account for those cases.

Test procedure:

7. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
8. Charge with constant current stated in the data sheet until the upper cut-off voltage is reached. If no value is given charge with the defined reference current rate.
9. Charge with constant voltage until the cut-off current stated in the data sheet is reached. If no value is stated use 0.1C.
10. Let the cell rest for 10 minutes.
11. Discharge with constant current stated in the data sheet until the upper cut-off voltage is reached. If no value is given charge with the defined reference current rate.
12. Discharge with constant voltage until the cut-off current stated in the data sheet is reached. If no value is stated use 0.1C.
13. Repeat steps 1-6 until the EOL criterion is reached. If the above procedure is modified, the “capacity measurement procedure” should be conducted periodically (e.g., every 50 cycles for commercial cells) to measure the real capacity.

Evaluation:

- Extract the cell thickness at 0 % SOC for every cycle and plot over the cycle number.
- Calculate the difference in cell thickness between 0 % and 100 % SOC for every cycle and plot over the cycle number.

Figure 13: Irreversible change in thickness over cycle life in a) and reversible expansion over cycles in b).

5.5 Maximal expansion at End of Life

The maximum of expansion is determined together with its dependence on pressure. Repeat the procedure and evaluation from 5.1.

An exemplary comparison between two cells at BOL and EOL is given in Figure 14. Since the dilation is merely completely caused by the anode, the features visible in the curves can be used to analyse the causes of the cell ageing. The positions of the kinks show the change of usable capacity of the anode, the shift of the stage 2 kink towards higher SOC means that the anode is only partially lithiated. Furthermore, the expansion of the plateau area is less high. This can be cause either by loss of anode active material or the ongoing compression of the pouch cell under pressure. It is expected that while the thickness of the overall cell is increasing,

the change in dilation per cycle is approximately proportional to the charge throughput in a full cycle. With less capacity the change in thickness is therefore lower.

Figure 14: expansion during pOCV measurement at EOL in a) and BOL in b).

5.6 Software

The evaluation of open-circuit data with integrated cycle life and hysteresis analysis can be done by the Matlab code package that was developed in parallel to this test protocol. The code is publicly available on [Zenodo](#) [27].

References

- [1] IEA, Grid-Scale Storage, 2022. <https://www.iea.org/reports/grid-scale-storage>.
- [2] Y. Nishi, Lithium ion secondary batteries; past 10 years and the future, *Journal of Power Sources* 100 (2001) 101–106. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(01\)00887-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(01)00887-4).
- [3] M.N. Obrovac, V.L. Chevrier, Alloy negative electrodes for Li-ion batteries, *Chem. Rev.* 114 (2014) 11444–11502. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr500207g>.
- [4] D. Billaud, F.X. Henry, M. Lelaurain, P. Willmann, Revisited structures of dense and dilute stage II lithium-graphite intercalation compounds, *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids* 57 (1996) 775–781. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3697\(95\)00348-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-3697(95)00348-7).
- [5] D. Billaud, F. Henry, Structural studies of the stage III lithium–graphite intercalation compound, *Solid State Communications* 124 (2002) 299–304. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-1098\(02\)00469-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-1098(02)00469-6).
- [6] C. Daniel, J.O. Besenhard, *Handbook of battery materials*, second., completely revised and enlarged edition, reprinted., Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2012.
- [7] M.T. McDowell, S.W. Lee, W.D. Nix, Y. Cui, 25th anniversary article: Understanding the lithiation of silicon and other alloying anodes for lithium-ion batteries, *Adv. Mater.* 25 (2013) 4966–4985. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201301795>.
- [8] J.H. Lee, H.M. Lee, S. Ahn, Battery dimensional changes occurring during charge/discharge cycles—thin rectangular lithium ion and polymer cells, *Journal of Power Sources* 119–121 (2003) 833–837. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753\(03\)00281-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-7753(03)00281-7).
- [9] M. Bauer, M. Wachtler, H. Stöwe, J.V. Persson, M.A. Danzer, Understanding the dilation and dilation relaxation behavior of graphite-based lithium-ion cells, *Journal of Power Sources* 317 (2016) 93–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2016.03.078>.
- [10] B. Bitzer, A. Gruhle, A new method for detecting lithium plating by measuring the cell thickness, *Journal of Power Sources* 262 (2014) 297–302. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2014.03.142>.
- [11] F. Grimsman, F. Brauchle, T. Gerbert, A. Gruhle, M. Knipper, J. Parisi, Hysteresis and current dependence of the thickness change of lithium-ion cells with graphite anode, *Journal of Energy Storage* 12 (2017) 132–137. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2017.04.006>.
- [12] M. Bauer, B. Rieger, S. Schindler, P. Keil, M. Wachtler, M.A. Danzer, A. Jossen, Multi-phase formation induced by kinetic limitations in graphite-based lithium-ion cells: Analyzing the effects on dilation and voltage response, *Journal of Energy Storage* 10 (2017) 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2016.11.006>.
- [13] F.B. Spingler, W. Wittmann, J. Sturm, B. Rieger, A. Jossen, Optimum fast charging of lithium-ion pouch cells based on local volume expansion criteria, *Journal of Power Sources* 393 (2018) 152–160. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.04.095>.
- [14] G. Fuchs, L. Willenberg, F. Ringbeck, D.U. Sauer, Post-Mortem Analysis of Inhomogeneous Induced Pressure on Commercial Lithium-Ion Pouch Cells and Their Effects, *Sustainability* 11 (2019) 6738. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11236738>.
- [15] V. Müller, R.-G. Scurtu, M. Memm, M.A. Danzer, M. Wohlfahrt-Mehrens, Study of the influence of mechanical pressure on the performance and aging of Lithium-ion battery cells, *Journal of Power Sources* 440 (2019) 227148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.227148>.

- [16] L. Jahn, F. Katzer, M.A. Danzer, Combined dilatometry and voltage analysis for a reliable detection of lithium deposition on graphitic anodes, *Journal of Power Sources* 520 (2022) 230870. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2021.230870>.
- [17] P. Kargl, V. Drews, P. Daubinger, O. Schweighofer, M. Marinaro, G.A. Giffin, M. Wohlfahrt-Mehrens, A. Thaler, Investigation of voltage and expansion hysteresis of Si-alloy-C/NMC622 pouch cells using dilatometry, *Journal of Power Sources* 548 (2022) 232042. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.232042>.
- [18] V. Müller, R.-G. Scurtu, K. Richter, T. Waldmann, M. Memm, M.A. Danzer, M. Wohlfahrt-Mehrens, Effects of Mechanical Compression on the Aging and the Expansion Behavior of Si/C-Composite|NMC811 in Different Lithium-Ion Battery Cell Formats, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 166 (2019) A3796-A3805. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.1121915jes>.
- [19] T. Deich, S.L. Hahn, S. Both, K.P. Birke, A. Bund, Validation of an actively-controlled pneumatic press to simulate automotive module stiffness for mechanically representative lithium-ion cell aging, *Journal of Energy Storage* 28 (2020) 101192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2020.101192>.
- [20] T. Deich, M. Storch, K. Steiner, A. Bund, Effects of module stiffness and initial compression on lithium-ion cell aging, *Journal of Power Sources* 506 (2021) 230163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2021.230163>.
- [21] H. Pegel, O. von Kessel, P. Heugel, T. Deich, J. Tübke, K.P. Birke, D.U. Sauer, Volume and thickness change of NMC811 | SiO_x-graphite large-format lithium-ion cells: from pouch cell to active material level, *Journal of Power Sources* 537 (2022) 231443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2022.231443>.
- [22] B. Rieger, S.F. Schuster, S.V. Erhard, P.J. Osswald, A. Rheinfeld, C. Willmann, A. Jossen, Multi-directional laser scanning as innovative method to detect local cell damage during fast charging of lithium-ion cells, *Journal of Energy Storage* 8 (2016) 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2016.09.002>.
- [23] R. Li, D. Ren, D. Guo, C. Xu, X. Fan, Z. Hou, L. Lu, X. Feng, X. Han, M. Ouyang, Volume Deformation of Large-Format Lithium Ion Batteries under Different Degradation Paths, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 166 (2019) A4106-A4114. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0471916jes>.
- [24] W. Ren, T. Zheng, C. Piao, D.E. Benson, X. Wang, H. Li, S. Lu, Characterization of commercial 18,650 Li-ion batteries using strain gauges, *J Mater Sci* 57 (2022) 13560–13569. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10853-022-07490-4>.
- [25] R. Hickey, T.M. Jahns, Measuring Individual Battery Dimensional Changes for State-of-Charge Estimation using Strain Gauge Sensors, in: 2019 IEEE Energy Conversion Congress and Exposition (ECCE), Baltimore, MD, USA, IEEE, 9/29/2019 - 10/3/2019, pp. 2460–2465.
- [26] M. Nagayama, K. Ariyoshi, Y. Yamamoto, T. Ohzuku, Characterization of Lithium Insertion Electrodes by Precision Dilatometer: Area-Specific Deformation of Single Electrode, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 161 (2014) A1388-A1393. <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0981409jes>.
- [27] L. Jahn, HysKaDi - open circuit measurements evaluation tool (Matlab) (2024). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13121433>.